

CONTEMPORARY URBAN GOVERNANCE INNOVATION DESIGN

Principles, Tools, and an Innovation Typology

JOEL TERWILLIGER | NET ZERO FUTURES BRIEF SERIES NO.1 OF 5

RESEARCH FOCUS AND POLICY CONTEXT

Cities are at the forefront of the global net zero transition, yet the governance landscape supporting them is increasingly fragmented. An expanding universe of transnational initiatives—such as the UN Cities Race to Zero and the EU NetZeroCities (NZC) Mission Platform—have contributed to a rapid proliferation of Procedural Governance Tools (PGTs): impact frameworks, climate action planning templates, and monitoring systems. Despite significant proliferation of climate initiatives and PGTs, current governance arrangements are insufficient for net zero at scale. The key challenge is a failure of siloed governance: analysis across 25 PGTs from four major networks reveals a consistent gap between common governance innovation design principles and the realities of practice, including persistent capacity challenges in frontrunner and less-resourced cities.

KEY FINDINGS

The REPAIR framework reveals that leading tools share a common ideal of seamless integration across multiple domains, while failing to address the hidden institutional and political factors needed for coherence. Alongside REPAIR, the brief outlines an innovation typology—governance, social, financial, and learning—rooted in EU and UK city support ecosystem definitions. Through Bristol case and comparative Mission city work, the typology is refined to form the Innovation Diamond: a conceptual model of an enabling innovation ecosystem supported by the intersectionality of domains—with learning innovation as the connective thread. In practice, these domains are often developed in isolation, and without deliberate bridging they pull in different directions, creating fragmentation rather than the coherent enabling conditions for net zero transformation.

KEY MESSAGES FOR POLICY AND PRACTICE

- **Governance innovation is an investment, not a given.** The 'people work' of building trust, aligning institutions, and sustaining participatory processes must be explicitly resourced — it cannot be absorbed by already-stretched cities.
- **Mind the gap between tool design intentions and operational realities.** Cities face a crowded, overlapping landscape of fragmented frameworks. More focus on co-design and co-refinement for tool alignment and practical applications is needed over addition.
- **Use the Innovation Diamond to map urban innovation ecosystems.** It provides a starting point for identifying where governance, social, financial, and learning innovations are the strongest, where the connections between them are weakest, and where to start.
- **Use REPAIR as a diagnostic.** Rather than adding new frameworks, assess existing initiatives against REPAIR's six dimensions to identify where new governance investments are most needed — and fund alignment work over new tools wherever possible.
- **Carbon metrics alone cannot tell you whether governance is working.** Monitoring systems must capture qualitative governance outcomes alongside quantitative carbon outputs and be genuinely reflexive, not a linear reporting exercise.

ABOUT THE NET ZERO FUTURES (NZF) STUDY AND THIS SERIES

Cities across Europe and the UK are investing heavily in net zero governance innovation—developing ambitious plans, new institutional arrangements, and citizen engagement processes—yet the gap between governance ambition and practice remains wide. The NZF study (2022–2026) examined why. Its central question: how can cities effectively mobilise resources to implement inclusive, participatory net zero strategies aligned with SDG goals?

■ **Phase 1** mapped 25 governance tools across UK, EU, and global contexts to develop the REPAIR framework, trace the emerging Climate City Contract (CCC) mechanism as both a governance innovation tool and process, and build an innovation typology grounded in urban governance success factors.

■ **Phase 2** involved six months embedded within the NetZeroCities (NZC) Mission Platform, followed by a case study of Bristol's Net Zero Investment Co-Innovation Lab, drawing on 16 interviews across three stakeholder clusters. Across phases, 24 informational interviews with 22 experts were conducted to identify perspectives and relevant research agendas.

■ **The NZF Series** draws on different elements of that empirical and analytical base. **Brief 1** presents the core conceptual tools used to trace climate strategy processes in cities; **Brief 2** puts the CCC and impact-oriented approaches of Mission cities in the context of the global urban climate governance system; **Briefs 3 and 4** explore the toolkit, operationalisation of just transition concepts, and stakeholder insights from the Bristol case; **Brief 5** synthesises insights and offers reflections for future research and practice.

The Proliferation of Procedural Governance Tools

A central finding of the NZF research is the rapid expansion of procedural governance tools (PGTs)—structured approaches that shape how decisions are made, actors are engaged, and policies are implemented in urban net zero governance. These tools circulate rapidly through transnational climate networks and initiatives, such as Energy Cities and the UN Cities Race to Resilience campaign and are adopted and adapted by cities with varying levels of institutional capacity and contextual fit.

PGTs are designed to facilitate collaboration across actors, structure planning and implementation processes, and enable knowledge exchange and learning.

However, analysis of 25 PGTs across four major networks shows that tools are proliferating faster than the governance infrastructure needed to integrate them. Cities are confronted with a crowded landscape of overlapping, sometimes contradictory frameworks without a coherent meta-framework for aligning them. This fragmentation reflects the competitive, project-based funding environment in which both cities and the organisations that support them operate, which incentivises the creation of new tools over the harder work of building coherence.

The REPAIR framework was developed to address this challenge—providing an analytical lens for evaluating governance innovations not individually but in terms of their collective contribution to the enabling conditions for transformative, just, and reflexive net zero governance.

The REPAIR Framework: Six Design Principles for Governance Innovation

The REPAIR framework (Terwilliger and Christie, 2025) synthesises six governance innovation design principles from analysis of 25 PGTs drawn from four transnational networks: the EU 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities Mission, Energy Cities, and the UN Cities Race to Zero and Race to Resilience campaigns. Each principle (shown in [Figure 1](#)) captures an “ideal type” dimension of governance that consistently emerges in leading tools and initiatives—and that is frequently disconnected from the often hidden institutional and political dynamics in practice.

Reflexivity — the capacity of governance systems to listen, learn, and adapt — is a foundational dimension of REPAIR, and the one most relevant to PGTs as instruments of governance.

Figure 1. The REPAIR Governance Innovation Framework. Own Illustration.

It encompasses internal and external feedback loops, monitoring and evaluation systems, organisational learning processes, and the institutional restructuring needed to embed learning into governance routines rather than treating it as a project-specific activity. **Enabling/Embedding** captures the importance of deep, sustained dialogue and the institutionalisation of learning into policy routines. **Participatory** governance emphasises cross-sectoral inclusion, values-driven processes, and multi-stakeholder partnerships. **Adaptivity** foregrounds agility—the ability to shift tools, working cultures, and models in response to new evidence. **Integrative** governance attends to the need for long-term, systemic change across multiple levers and governance scales. **Radicality** recognises that transformative net zero governance requires holistic system innovation, including alternative visions and voices not typically represented in formal planning.

These six principles are not a checklist but interconnected, often tension-generating dimensions of governance that must be navigated in context. The REPAIR framework is designed as both a diagnostic and a design tool: helping researchers and practitioners assess where existing governance innovations are strong, where they fall short, and where new investments in institutional capacity are most needed.

Reflexivity in Missions: Reflexive MEL in Urban Climate Governance

REPAIR's Reflexivity dimension is illustrated through the NZC platform's approach to local Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning (MEL) system design, which seeks to break out of the traditional project cycle (design-implement-deliver-report) toward continuous, collective strategic learning. The NZC impact pathways, MEL process, and Comprehensive Indicator Framework (CIF) collectively constitute the NZC Theory of Change (ToC) and act as a backbone to the Climate City Contract (CCC). The NZC ToC/MEL approach is designed to be more dynamic than traditional linear planning: rather than treating monitoring as reporting at the end of the chain, it aims for real-time and continuous reflexivity, or 'learning loops,' as the 'L' of the MEL system.

NZC experts articulate the ambition for transforming urban climate governance: Reflexive MEL involves continuously questioning assumptions, engaging diverse perspectives, and learning-by-doing so that policies can adapt over time (NetZeroCities, 2025).

This integration of reflexive MEL in urban climate governance is characterised as a shift towards more adaptive, inclusive, and transformative approaches to addressing climate change at the city level—an ambition that **Brief 2** examines across Mission cities’ climate strategies. **Table 1** below presents the NZC MEL definitions linked to the academic literature that underpin this approach—defining what monitoring, evaluation, and learning each require to be genuinely reflexive rather than merely procedural. Taken together, these definitions point toward experimental forms of governance: decision-

making systems that are adaptive (adjusting strategies based on learning), inclusive (drawing on diverse perspectives including community knowledge), and transformative (seeking systemic change rather than incremental optimisation). This is a more demanding governance standard than most cities are currently meeting—and a more demanding standard than most monitoring requirements are designed to evaluate. This gap between the vision of reflexive MEL and its operationalisation in practice is one of the central governance challenges documented across the NZF study.

Table 1
NZC MEL and Best Practice Definitions Used by NZC Experts

Component	Definition, Linked to Literature
Monitoring	Should entail broad collaboration among stakeholders, innovative metrics to track progress and co-benefits, and feedback loops that integrate learning into decision-making (Ansell and Torfing, 2021)
Evaluation	Needs to go beyond traditional success metrics to encompass a more holistic assessment of progress towards sustainability goals. It involves not only measuring quantitative outcomes but also qualitative changes in governance structures, social dynamics, and urban systems (Wolfram et al., 2019)
Learning	(Collective learning) needs to involve diverse stakeholders, from policymakers to citizens, in co-creating and implementing sustainable urban futures (Frantzeskaki and Rok, 2018)

An Innovation Typology: Four Enabling Domains

Alongside REPAIR, the NZF study introduces a four-part innovation typology drawing from the broader literature on urban transitions, with a focus on the urban governance innovation success factors identified by (Roll et al., 2022): stakeholder involvement, financial resources, and impact assessment. Each type represents a distinct domain of enabling activity—and together they constitute the building blocks of a local innovation ecosystem for net zero transformation. The typology was initially developed deductively from mapping how each are defined within the EU NetZeroCities and UK Net Zero Living programme support ecosystems and subsequently refined through empirical engagement with the Bristol case and insights from fellow “Mission cities”.

Governance Innovation centres on the tools and institutional arrangements through which local governments align current actions with a net zero future—using more open, participatory, and experimental approaches under conditions of complexity and uncertainty.

Social Innovation is a collaborative, human-centric approach for cities to cultivate enabling ecosystems by co-designing new ideas with residents and changing norms and systems of governance. **Financial Innovation** involves working in new ways with actors to mobilise finance, shape low-carbon markets, and develop new blended finance models, such as combining public, private, and citizen crowdfunding sources. **Learning Innovation** encompasses strategic learning activities and processes using procedural tools designed to support new ways of working identified via ‘learning by doing’ experiments—capturing nontraditional forms of expertise and evidence, including hard-to-define co-benefits and local insights.

The four types (core definitions in **Table 2**) are not siloed—they interact, depend upon, and sometimes contradict one another. Effective net zero governance requires coherence across all four domains: innovations that are strong in one area but weak in others risk amplifying existing inequities rather than addressing them. This coherence requirement is the analytical foundation for the NZC governance mosaic analysis that follows.

Table 2
Innovation Types and Key Definitions

Type	Definitions Across UK and EU City Support Ecosystems
Governance	Novel rules, regulations, and approaches that seek to address a public problem in more effective ways, lead to better policy outcomes, and enhance legitimacy (Anheier and Korreck, 2013; NetZeroCities, 2022). The tools and institutional arrangements through which local governments align current actions with a net zero future and manage associated challenges (Velten et al., 2023, p. 162) using more open, participatory, co-creative, and experimental approaches under conditions of complexity and uncertainty (European Environment Agency, 2024, p. 19).
Social	A collaborative and human-centric approach for cities to cultivate an enabling ecosystem for net zero by/with residents to co-design new ideas and solutions as well as change norms and systems of governance (Caulier-Grice et al., 2012; NetZeroCities, 2023). A form of innovation that is social in its ends and its means (Murray, Caulier-Grice and Mulgan, 2010). In the context of NetZeroCities pilot initiatives, this means developing new ideas, services, and models that better address social challenges, and more broadly, innovation that is “social” in its objectives, processes, and outcomes (NetZeroCities, 2022).
Financial	Working in new ways with actors to mobilise finance, shape low-carbon markets/demand, and develop new/blended finance models (blending public, private, and citizen crowdfunding sources). Own definition based on the following: The act of creating and then popularising new financial instruments as well as new financial technologies, institutions, and markets (Tufano, 2003, p. 310). Creating blueprints and business models that are being tested under a learning-by-doing approach, creating deep and long-lasting transformative change, and establishing coordinating mechanisms with new critical players (Ulpiani et al., 2023). Creating business models for the area-based funding of net zero projects by enabling economies of scale, attracting investment, and enabling cross-subsidy (Greater SE Net Zero Hub, no date).
Learning	Strategic learning activities and processes using PGTs designed to support new ways of working identified via “learning by doing” experiments, involving deliberate organisational efforts to develop/formalise learning systems that capture nontraditional forms of expertise/evidence (e.g., social and community-based learning). Own definition based on (Pahl-Wostl, 2009; OPSI, 2018; Mulgan, 2022; NetZeroCities, no date)

The NZC Platform: A Governance Innovation Mosaic

The NetZeroCities Mission Platform is analysed in NZF as a case study in governance innovation at scale. The platform supports 112 ‘Trailblazer’ cities through a suite of interlocking tools, learning networks, and support mechanisms, all oriented around the Climate City Contract (CCC) as both a governance innovation tool and a collaborative learning process.

Figure 2 maps the theoretical foundations and multi-level institutional architecture of this mosaic (see (Terwilliger and Christie, 2025) for more detail).

The mosaic illustrates how the CCC sits at the intersection of multiple theoretical traditions—mission-oriented innovation, transition management, social innovation, and multi-level governance—and how the NZC platform translates these concepts into concrete support mechanisms.

Figure 2. The NZC Platform Governance Innovation Mosaic and Support Structure. Own Illustration.

National platforms (e.g., Viable Cities in Sweden), City Support Groups, sensemaking activities, and the Pilot Cities Programme all contribute to what NZC describes as 'strategic learning loops': iterative cycles of doing, reflecting, and adapting. In practice, these loops function unevenly:

stronger in cities with existing institutional infrastructure and relationships, fragile or absent in less-resourced cities. Some key Mission components and operational functions are given below in [Table 3](#). Their effectiveness is shaped by the concepts and tensions documented in [Table 4](#).

Table 3 EU Cities Mission Components and Functions	
Component	Operational Function
Climate City Contract (CCC)	Serves as the central procedural governance tool to support cities in iterating commitments, action plans, and investment plans across silos to formalise governance innovation.
City Support Groups	Facilitates strategic learning on enabling urban innovation activities through dedicated city advisors and subject matter experts, in connection with peer-to-peer twinning and pilot programme cohorts and systemic sensemaking activities.
Mission Label & Capital Hub	Unlocks financial innovation by providing technical assistance for project development and capital facilitation, connecting public/private institutions to Mission cities (cities with CCCs that have been validated and awarded the Mission Label).
NZC Theory of Change	Supports learning innovation processes via Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning (MEL) loops, utilising a comprehensive indicator framework to assess early and later outcomes of identified Climate City Contract implementation priorities and inform iterative planning.

[Table 4](#) provides a simplified summary of the key governance concepts embedded in the NZC platform, their practical applications, and their most significant limitations—as identified

through the NZF study's analysis of NZC documents, expert interviews, and stakeholder observations across the platform.

Table 4
Key NZC Governance Concepts: Applications and Limitations

Concept	NZC Application	Limitation
Mission Approach	Structures grand challenges (e.g., climate neutrality by 2030) into portfolio-based governance, with public sector-led cross-sectoral co-creation and radical collaboration to unlock (e.g., net zero) pathways and co-investment.	Sets a broad direction but lacks specificity on the how of managing the complexities of inclusive governance and project pipelines; mission formulation, integration, and implementation processes remain underspecified.
Governance Innovation	The CCC as both a governance tool and a collaborative process: building collective intelligence, enabling experimental governance, and fostering alignment across institutional levels.	Horizontal (cross-departmental) has progressed and vertical (multi-level) alignment remains partial; CCC ambition frequently outpaces cities' institutional capacities.
Transition Management	NZC support structures (sensemaking, peer learning, twinning) designed to sustain reflexive learning loops and strategic experimentation across the platform's 112 cities.	Monitoring, Evaluation, and Learning (MEL) practice is hindered by high workloads and fragmented co-benefits frameworks; most cities lack capacity for continuous participatory processes.
Social Innovation	Community co-design, resident engagement, and multi-stakeholder partnerships embedded in CCC processes to build shared ownership and a local mandate for net zero action.	Participation remains largely conceptual in CCC guidance; monitoring requirements focus on emissions reduction, not governance process quality or equity outcomes.
Multi-level Governance	National platforms (e.g., Viable Cities/Sweden, citiES2030/Spain) support institutional climate action coordination, adapting EU Cities Mission tools and approaches and connecting cities with the national level and key stakeholders.	National platform support is uneven; most Mission city countries lack formal multi-level alignment and support structures, leaving cities dependent on fragile, project-based funding and informal platforms.
Co-Benefits Approach	Cities develop socio-economic cases for decarbonising using a portfolio approach to unlock synergies and co-benefits between diverse sectoral actions.	Helpful in mainstreaming climate action to leverage finance but often ignores the political dynamics and power relations inherent in prioritising action portfolios.

A Refined Typology: Towards an Enabling Ecosystem

The initial four-part typology was refined through empirical and comparative engagement over the course of the NZF study. Drawing on 16 stakeholder interviews with 18 experts across the public sector, knowledge and advisory sector,

and VCSE (Voluntary, Community and Social Enterprise) sector—and triangulated with expert outputs, the model in [Figure 3](#) shows the interrelation of innovation types towards an 'enabling ecosystem for urban transformations.' The refinement distils the essence of each domain. Progressing transformative urban governance depends on their integration, with a focus on where they can be mutually reinforcing.

Figure 3. Innovation Diamond for an Enabling Urban Transformation Ecosystem. Own Illustration.

In practice, these domains are often developed separately and connections between them are weak or implicitly assumed to be 'seamless.' Governance innovation advances through new structures, processes, and coordination mechanisms for city-led cross-sector collaboration; financial innovation through novel co-investment planning, alternative finance models, and diverse forms of resource mobilisation; social innovation through community- and citizen-led co-design and inclusion (e.g., planning by/with residents); and learning innovation through systems for integrating knowledge production and use (expert/technical with place-based/experiential). Each area can generate real progress within its own logic—but without deliberate bridging across domains, they often pull in different directions, creating fragmentation rather than the coherent enabling conditions that net zero transformation requires.

Learning innovation plays a particularly integrative role in this model. Making the link between collective action and collective learning—via iterative 'strategic learning loops' that capture diverse insights—means expanding the evidence base beyond traditional metrics to incorporate governance

process and mixed qualitative-quantitative co-benefits monitoring. The vision for a truly reflexive MEL in practice looks like: not a separate, linear reporting exercise, but the connective thread that weaves governance, social, and financial innovation together and enables them to adapt over time.

A key recognition across Mission Cities is the need to bring these different activities together in service of this enabling ecosystem—and this requires confronting a harder question than which PGTs are used: sharing power and responsibility with a wider group of people. This 'radical collaboration' requires new relations between groups that haven't necessarily worked together in this way before. It raises practical questions of how efforts can be aligned as 'pieces of the jigsaw': creating a shared theory of change; influencing how net zero can create locally beneficial change; and navigating tensions over who is responsible for what. The Bristol Lab case, examined in [Brief 4](#), traces how one frontrunner city is progressing efforts to develop a place-based innovation model that looks beyond return on investment and technical solutions toward these systemic enabling conditions.

What's Next in the Series

This is [Brief 1](#) of the NZF Series, summarising the doctoral thesis of Joel Terwilliger: **Towards More Participatory Net Zero Futures (2022-2026)**, supervised by Ian Christie, Stelvia Matos, and Subhes Bhattacharyya. The next titles in the series are: ([Brief 2](#)) Valuing What Matters in Urban Climate Governance: Co-Benefits Gaps and Functions in Making the Case for Action; ([Brief 3](#)) Governing a Just Net Zero Transition: The Bristol Toolkit and City and Community Visions for Change; ([Brief 4](#)) Governing Net Zero Missions: Innovation, Alignment, and Mobilisation Insights from Bristol and Fellow Cities; and ([Brief 5](#)) Missions, Myths, and Contemporary Procedural Governance Tools: Reflections and a Proposed Research Agenda.

KEY INSIGHTS & POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

For Policymakers and Funders

- Treat governance as a core investment, not a given. The 'people work' of building trust, aligning institutions, and sustaining participatory processes is a hidden cost that must be explicitly resourced—not absorbed by already-stretched local authorities. Adequately resourcing and allowing flexibility for engagement processes is needed rather than expecting time and place-based insights from civil society and citizens for free.
- Use REPAIR as a diagnostic tool. Rather than adding new governance frameworks to an already-crowded landscape, assess existing initiatives against the six REPAIR dimensions to identify where investments in reflexivity, participation, and radicality are most needed.
- Require governance process indicators alongside carbon metrics. Monitoring systems that only track emissions cannot evaluate whether governance innovation is building the enabling conditions for a just, inclusive transition. MEL systems must be designed to capture qualitative governance outcomes, not just quantitative carbon outputs.
- Design for innovation coherence, not just 'new-to-market' frameworks and decision-support tools. The proliferation of PGTs increases complexity without improving effectiveness when tools are not integrated around shared theories of change. Fund alignment work as explicitly as tool development.

For Mission-Minded Cities and Practitioners

- Map innovation ecosystem enablers across all Innovation Diamond domains. Identify where governance, social, financial, and learning innovations are advancing in isolation—and where the connections between them are weakest. This mapping can support prioritising enabling actions and act as a starting point for meaningful integration.
- Develop living, participatory theories of change. The NZC MEL vision of reflexive, adaptive governance cannot be realised through static strategic documents. Build on your internal understanding of possible action areas through regular, multi-stakeholder review processes that bring community knowledge into planning cycles alongside technical and financial expertise.

- Invest in 'anchor people' to develop and maintain both horizontal (cross-departmental) and vertical (multi-level) alignment around common climate-related goals. Champions who can bridge community knowledge and institutional processes, translate between logics, and maintain momentum through political cycles are essential—and fragile. Structural support for these roles is critical.

For Researchers

- Apply REPAIR as a comparative analytical lens. The framework offers a multi-dimensional tool for evaluating governance innovations across cities, networks, and scales—and for identifying where the gap between radicality and reality is widest in both PGTs and their operationalisation.
- Prioritise governance process indicator development. Empirical evidence on how PGTs are operationalised—including their equity implications and unintended consequences—is urgently needed. REPAIR provides a starting point for the governance process indicators that MEL systems currently lack. For example, co-developing specific, verifiable metrics for evaluating non-technical, relational processes within Transition Teams to ensure accountability for equitable decision-making and power-sharing.

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